

Ranking of Wikipedia Articles in Search Engines. Partial Replication of the Study “Ranking of Wikipedia Articles Revisited” from 2011

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1. Introduction

Wikipedia has struggled with its academic reputation since its launch in 2001. While it has been the subject of many different accusations such as plagiarism (Jemielniak and Aibar, 2016, p. 1773), recent studies on the quality of information of Wikipedia articles have produced positive results (Anderka und Stein, 2012; Redi et al., 2019; Halfaker, 2017). Several retrieval studies discuss the prominent position of Wikipedia articles in search engine result pages (SERPs). In 2011, Lewandowski and Spree explored the question of whether the high information quality of Wikipedia articles can predict high ranking in SERPs and whether there is a relationship between ranking, information quality and perceived relevance of Wikipedia articles. I present with this poster a partial replication of Lewandowski and Spree's study.

2. Method

Both the studies by Lewandowski (2008) on the retrieval effectiveness of search engines and the study on the ranking, relevance and information quality of Wikipedia articles by Lewandowski and Spree (2011) were relevant for the design of this study. Forty informational search queries and their first ten results in the search engines Google, Bing, DuckDuckGo (DDG) and Ecosia were analysed. The retrieval study was conducted using the Result Assessment Tool (RAT)¹. For the relevance assessment, eleven jurors were asked to rate the relevance of the retrieved Wikipedia results, by giving a judgement as to whether they found the result relevant in terms of the quality of the result, taking into account the search query. For the information quality evaluation, the heuristic for the evaluation of encyclopedia articles by Lewandowski and Spree was reused. Additionally, a second version of the heuristic was adapted to current Wikipedia internal quality criteria as well as supplemented by quality flaw criteria identified in Anderka and Stein's study (2012).

3. Results

The retrieval study identified 138 Wikipedia results (47 of which were unique). The mean position of Wikipedia articles is statistically significantly higher (2.97) than that of other websites (5.74), regardless of the search engine used. The relevance study shows positive results for the questions of whether and how relevant the Wikipedia results are from the perspective of the jurors. This is depicted by the mean binary judgement of 90 % (“is relevant”) as well as the mean score of the 5-point-scale of 2.91 (“how relevant”: 0 to 4). The heuristic evaluation shows that the overall scores vary considerably, but in the higher score range. The highest rated article achieves 89 % of the maximum score. Articles were rated positively in terms of comprehensiveness but received lower ratings for the

¹ <https://searchstudies.org/rat-software/>

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currency of sources and the verifiability of facts as many articles lacked direct references. There are moderate correlations between both perceived relevance and ranking positions (-0.5) as well as between the binary relevance scores and the scores in the heuristic evaluation of the information quality (0.4). There is a weak correlation between the information quality and the ranking (original heuristic: 0.3; adapted heuristic: 0.2).

4. Discussion and Conclusion

The results show that the users' judgements of relevance are consistent with the high ranking and the data in the original study. This comparison also shows, that the Wikipedia articles have improved significantly in terms of content and comprehensiveness, but worsened in the aspects of currency and verifiability. Although information quality improved overall, data shows that high ranking does not necessarily mean high information quality.

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